

The Valency of Boron.

BY

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From the chemical point of view, boron is decidedly a non-metallic element. It is trivalent in its halogen derivatives and the trivalent nature is also exhibited in most of its compounds. However, under certain conditions it appears to possess a valency of five. Moissan (Compt. rend., 1892, 115, 271) has prepared boron penta-sulphide. A few other compounds of boron, containing organic radicles, such as $C_6H_5.B.Cl$, $(CH_3)_3.B:NH_3$, $C_2H_5(C_2H_5O)_2B:B(OC_2H_5)_3$, $(C_2H_5O)_3.B.OC_2H_5.Na$, etc., described by Michaelis and Becker (Ber. 1880, 13, 58); Frankland and Duppa (Phil. Trans., 1862, 152, 167; Proc. Roy. Soc., 1876, 25, 165), and Copaux (Compt., rend., 1898, 127, 719) probably contains pentavalent boron and may be formulated thus:—

The compound $(CH_3)_3B:NH_3$ is fairly stable; it melts at 51° and boils at 110° . The existence of certain additive compounds of boron trihaloids also suggests the pentavalent nature of the element.

Stock and his co-workers (Stock and Massenez, Ber., 1912, 45, 3539; Stock and Frederici, *ibid.*, 1913, 46, 1959; Stock, Frederici and Priess, *ibid.*, 1913, 46, 3353; Stock, Z. Electrochem., 1913, 19, 779; Stock, Kuss and Priess, Ber., 1914, 47, 3115) have suggested that boron is quadrivalent in the case of its hydrides and certain compounds derived from it, but except in cases in which the composition of the substance is doubtful or the molecular formulæ has not been determined, it is possible to assign formulæ to all these compounds on the assumption that boron is always trivalent or pentavalent. Further, as has been pointed out by Huggins (J. Phys. Chem., 1922, 26, 833) "that in the light of the present-day evidence in regard to atomic structure, it does not seem likely that boron can be quadrivalent in the sense that carbon is quadrivalent—that in these substances each boron atom can directly be bonded, through electron pairs, to four other atoms." Huggins suggests that boron is trivalent in all the hydrides, and the hydrogen atoms are held by means of four electron bonds and each such four electron bond is surrounded by four atoms. For the four hydrides, B_2H_6 , B_4H_{10} , B_6H_{12} , and $B_{10}H_{16}$, Huggins assigns structures similar to those adopted by him (Jour. Am. Chem. Soc., 1922, 44, 1607; Science, 1922, 55, 678) for ethylene ($H_2C=CH_2$), butadiene ($H_3C=CH-CH=CH_2$), benzene (C_6H_6) and naphthalene ($C_{10}H_8$), respectively. But these unusual structures must be very unstable and although they may be strong enough for holding together the hydrogen atoms, they are extremely unsuitable for molecules having larger atomic kernels. They are incapable of explaining the structure of the borohydrates, which undoubtedly possess very similar constitution as the hydrides, as well as the halogen derivatives such as, B_2H_3Cl and $B_2H_4Cl_2$. It has been pointed out in a previous paper (Jour. Chem. Soc., 1922,

121, 1088) that the group,

appears to be a fairly stable one and is present in the hydrides, the borohydrates, the halogen derivatives of the hydrides, and Frankland's compound $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{B}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_2 : \text{B}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_3$.

The five hydrides of boron isolated by Stock and his collaborators (*l. c.*) may be assigned the following formulæ:—

- (1) $\text{B}_2\text{H}_6 \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{B} : \text{BH}_3$
- (2) $\text{B}_4\text{H}_{10} \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{B} : \text{BH}_2 \cdot \text{BH}_2 : \text{BH}_3$
- (3) $\text{B}_5\text{H}_9 \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{B} : \text{BH} : \text{BH} : \text{BH} : \text{BH}_3$
- (4) $\text{B}_6\text{H}_{10} \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{B} : \text{BH} : \text{BH} : \text{BH} : \text{BH} : \text{BH}_3$
- (5) $\text{B}_{10}\text{H}_{14} \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{B} : \text{BH} : \text{BH}_3$

To the borohydrate $\text{H}_4\text{B}_3(\text{OH})_2$, and the halogen derivatives, $\text{B}_2\text{H}_3\text{X}$ and $\text{B}_2\text{H}_4\text{X}_2$, all of which correspond to the hydride B_2H_6 , may be given the formulæ:—

The difficulty about the structure of the hydrides and the corresponding compounds disappears if the more natural assumption, that boron exhibits a negative valency of five in these compounds, be adopted. Frankland (*loc. cit.*) was the first to suggest the possibility of a quinquevalent boron atom corresponding to that

of nitrogen, phosphorus and arsenic. More recently, Hermans (Proc. K. Acad. Wetench. Amsterdam, 1923, 26, 32) has prepared the crystalline potassium salt of pyrocatecholboric acid, and its composition has been found to be $C_{12}H_8O_4 \cdot BK$. The only plausible structure is

and in all probability contains quinquevalent boron. In a paper on the valency of boron Böeseken (*ibid*, 1923, 26, 97) has discussed the possibility of the boron atom functioning as a quinquevalent and quadrivalent element according to the Lewis-Langmuir theory of valency. He has shown that the oldest known type of compound in which boron is to be regarded as quinquevalent is the type HBF_4 . In boron fluoride, BF_3 , the outer electron ring of the boron atom contains six electrons shared in pairs with the fluorine atoms. When combining with another molecule of hydrogen fluoride, the boron atom completes its octet by sharing with the new fluorine atom one of the electrons of the latter and a hydrogen electron. By taking the hydrogen electron, however, it forms the negative ion BF_4^- and the positive ion H^+ .

Of the modern theories of the structure of atoms, although the Lewis-Langmuir theory of fixed electrons appears better suited to explain chemical facts, the balance of evidence is in favour of Bohr's revolving electron quantum theory. According to the latter, the boron atom consists of the helium structure of two electrons revolving in uni-quantum orbits and in addition 3 electrons in 2-quantum orbits of type 2. These three electrons can each share the outer ring of three halogen atoms thus completing their octets or five additional electrons can gather round the boron atom and complete its own octet. This corresponds to Abegg and Bodlander's theory of Valency (Z. Anorg. Chem., 1899, 20, 453; *ibid*, 1904,

39, 330) which states that the sum of the maximum negative and positive valencies of an element equals eight. In the present considerations of the structure of the boron hydrides and borohydrates the compounds will be expressed in terms of the fixed electron atom, as this type of atom is more suitable for graphical representation. So far as the structures of the compounds are concerned they would remain almost the same whichever type of atom be assumed.

An important factor in determining the valency of an element is the place of the element in the atomic number scale relative to the place of the nearest non-valent gases. There are, thus, two valency-determining distances for each element, the one, the distance below a non-valent gas, determines the negative valency and the other, the distance above a non-valent gas, determines the positive valency of the element. Boron is three places above helium and five places below neon so that it is expected to possess a positive valency of three and a negative valency of five. The negative valency if it is exhibited at all, will be much weaker than the positive valency. If boron really exhibited a negative valency of five the question naturally arises, "Why does not a compound of the formula BH_5 exist?" It is easy to picture BH_5 as a neon system of electrons, completed by the single electrons of five hydrogen atoms with the five hydrogen nuclei arranged externally. By calculating the "mean collision areas" from the results of measurements of the viscosity of various gaseous hydrides, Rankine (Trans. Faraday Soc., 1922, 17, 719) has shown that as the number of hydrogen atoms in the molecule increases their nuclei become more and more remote from the nucleus of the central atom. He has suggested "that it is reasonable to suppose that this retreat of the hydrogen nuclei is due to the fact that they exert mutual

repulsion on one another, and that would naturally tend to drive them further apart with each addition. The effect finally leads to the failure to form such molecules as BH_5 , which may be theoretically possible but are unstable owing to the repulsion of the numerous hydrogen nuclei."

If this view is accepted, it is easy to understand the simultaneous formation of several hydrides of boron by the action of acids on magnesium boride. The molecules of BH_3 , which may be supposed to be temporarily formed, break up on account of the mutual repulsion of the hydrogen nuclei, and from this results the formation of several more complex molecules containing more than one atom of boron. The hydride B_2H_6 , for example, is formed by the linking of two BH_3 -groups and B_2H_{10} from two BH_3 -groups and two BH_2 -groups.

It has been shown by J. J. Thomson (Phil. Mag. 1921 [vi], 41, 520) that the attachment of a 1 one-electron atom like that of hydrogen requires two electrons on the layer round the atom with which it is combined. Lewis (Trans. Faraday. Soc., 1923, 19, 452) has emphasised the fact that the formation of the electron pair is the most important phenomenon in all chemical combinations. Although the quantum theory at present gives no adequate explanation of the pairing of electrons to form a single bond, and although it is difficult to reconcile it with the undoubted existence and apparent stability of H_2 (J. J. Thomson, *ibid.*, 1923, 19, 476) where one electron holds two nuclei together, the universality of this pairing of electrons in the binding of atoms appears to point definitely to an actual physical coupling of electronic orbits. As it is not possible for five hydrogen atoms to become attached to a single atom of boron, no hydride containing a single atom of boron is formed. The structure of the two gaseous hydrides, B_2H_6 and B_4H_{10}

may be illustrated thus:—

The two end hydrogen atoms, in the first compound are replaceable by hydroxyls or halogens and give rise to the compounds $B_2H_4(OH)_2$ and $B_2H_4X_2$. The suggested structure resembles the crystalline form of the potassium salt, $B_2H_4(OK)_2$, which crystallises as octahedrons. Little is known of the properties of the hydrides of boron and further experimental evidence is necessary before these or any other proposed structures may be considered as correct. For the investigation of the connection between atomic structure and chemical properties, however, the study of the boron atom in the formation of the hydrides and the related compounds is of great interest.

Summary.

(1) The valency of boron is discussed. Although in most of its compounds, the elements exhibit a positive valency of 3, under certain circumstances, especially in the case of the hydrides and certain related compounds, it appears to possess a negative valency of 5.

(2) Structures are proposed for the hydroborons, borohydrates, and the halogen derivatives of the boron hydrides.

In conclusion I wish to express my thanks to Prof. F. G. Donnan, F.R.S., and Dr. M. W. Travers, F.R.S., for their kind interest.

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[Received July 7, 1934]

